
ON GENERALIZED ADDITION CHAINS

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Abstract

Given integers $d \geq 1$, and $g \geq 2$, a g -addition chain for d is a sequence of integers $a_0 = 1, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{r-1}, a_r = d$ where $a_i = a_{j_1} + a_{j_2} + \dots + a_{j_k}$, with $2 \leq k \leq g$, and $0 \leq j_1 \leq j_2 \leq \dots \leq j_k \leq i - 1$. The length of a g -addition chain is r , the number of terms following 1 in the sequence. We denote by $l_g(d)$ the length of a shortest addition chain for d . Many results have been established in the case $g = 2$. Our aim is to establish the same sort of results for arbitrary fixed g . In particular, we adapt methods for constructing g -addition chains when $g = 2$ to the case $g > 2$ and we study the asymptotic behavior of l_g .

1. Introduction

Given integers $d \geq 1$, and $g \geq 2$, a g -addition chain for d is a sequence of integers

$$a_0 = 1, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{r-1}, a_r = d$$

where $a_i = a_{j_1} + a_{j_2} + \dots + a_{j_k}$, with $2 \leq k \leq g$, and $0 \leq j_1 \leq j_2 \leq \dots \leq j_k \leq i - 1$. The length of a g -addition chain is r , the number of terms following 1 in the sequence. We denote by $l_g(d)$ the length of a shortest addition chain for d .

Knuth [8] attributes the first mention of the problem of determining $l_2(d)$ to H. Dellac in 1894. Knuth also reports that E. de Jonquières in 1894 applied what is now known as the factor method to the computation of 2-addition chains. The term

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addition chain itself, meaning 2-addition chain, was coined and formally defined in 1937 by Scholz [9]. While many conjectures (and theorems!) concerning addition chains rose and fell over the years, the celebrated 1937 Scholz-Brauer conjecture, claiming that $l_2(2^n - 1) \leq n - 1 + l_2(n)$, remains open today.

The Scholz-Brauer conjecture and the intriguing behavior of the l_2 function led to an abundant literature on addition chains. Knuth [8, Section 4.6.3] is a careful source of facts and historical details covering the period up to 1973. Further developments, including world records and a bibliography reaching until 2008, can be found at [6].

To the best of our knowledge, none of the above literature considers g -addition chains for $g > 2$. We begin investigating such “generalized” addition chains here. Specifically, Section 2 describes three algorithms to generate g -addition chains. In Section 3, we establish upper and lower bounds on $l_g(d)$ and we bound the main term and the error term in the asymptotic behavior of $l_g(d)$. Section 4 concludes by recalling the algebraic complexity theory context in which the study of addition chains can be cast and by listing open questions and suggestions for future work.

When ς is a sequence of integers i_1, \dots, i_j and m is an integer, we let $m \cdot \varsigma$ stand for $m \cdot i_1, \dots, m \cdot i_j$. We also adopt the following notation:

- $\lfloor x \rfloor$ floor of x ;
- $\lceil x \rceil$ ceiling of x ;
- $\lambda_g(n)$ $\lfloor \log_g(n) \rfloor$
- $\mu_g(n)$ number of nonzero digits in the representation of n in basis g ;
- $l_g(n)$ length of a minimal g -addition chain for n ;
- $o(1)$ function $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $f(n)$ goes to 0 when n goes to infinity.

2. Construction of Generalized Addition Chains

In this section, we extend three methods used to generate 2-addition chains for the generation of g -addition chains, $g \geq 2$. We then compare the performances of the methods on selected infinite families of integers.

2.1. The Factor Method

For every $g \geq 2$ and $d \geq 1$, our extension to the factor method for 2-addition chains [8] produces a unique g -addition chain. This chain is obtained by crossing

out duplicates from the sequence $\text{fac}[d]$, defined by induction on d as

$$\begin{cases} 1, d & \text{if } d \leq g, \\ \text{fac} \left[\frac{d - (d \bmod g)}{g} \right], d - (d \bmod g), d & \text{else, if } d \text{ is prime,} \\ \text{fac}[p_1 p_2 \cdots p_i], (p_1 p_2 \cdots p_i) \cdot \text{fac}[p_{i+1} p_{i+2} \cdots p_m] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where the prime factorization of d is $p_1 p_2 \cdots p_m$ with $p_1 \leq p_2 \leq \cdots \leq p_m$ in the last case and i is the minimum j such that $p_1 p_2 \cdots p_j \geq g$, unless $j = m$, in which case i is set to $j - 1$.

Clearly $\text{fac}[d]$ is well-defined. Note that in the second case, $d - (d \bmod g)$ is obtained in one step by summing g occurrences of $\frac{d - (d \bmod g)}{g}$; then d is obtained by adding $d - (d \bmod g)$ to $(d \bmod g)$ occurrences of 1. In the third case, $(p_1 p_2 \cdots p_i) \cdot \text{fac}[p_{i+1} p_{i+2} \cdots p_m]$ is obtained by applying the steps defining the chain for $p_{i+1} p_{i+2} \cdots p_m$ starting from the last number $p_1 p_2 \cdots p_i$ of the chain obtained for $p_1 p_2 \cdots p_i$.

When $g = 2$, the above method precisely reduces to the factor method described in [8]. We note that the second case in our generalized method exploits the insight that when $g > 2$, merely computing $\text{fac}[d - (g - 1)]$ and then d would fail to ensure division by g in the recursive step. Finally, we note that a possible improvement in the third case would be to order the prime factors of d in such a way as to bring $p_1 p_2 \cdots p_j$ closest to g .

Example 2.1. Consider $d = (g + 1)^2$, where $g + 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ is the prime decomposition of $g + 1$ with $p_1 < \cdots < p_k$. Assume first that $k > 1$. Then $d = p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_k^{2\alpha_k}$. So the factor method induces the g -addition chain

$$1, \underbrace{p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i - 1}, p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i}}_{\text{fac}[p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i}]}, p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{2\alpha_i} \cdots p_k^{2\alpha_k}$$

where i and $0 < \beta_i \leq 2\alpha_i$ are the smallest integers such that $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i} \geq g$. Indeed since g does not divide $(g + 1)^2$, we have $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i} \geq g + 1$. Also, since $k > 1$, $p_1^{\alpha_1 + 1}$ divides $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i}$, so $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i} \neq g + 1$. Hence $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i} \geq g + 2$. Therefore, since $\frac{(g + 1)^2}{g + 2} < g + 1$, i.e., $\frac{(g + 1)^2}{g + 2} \leq g$, we have $p_i^{2\alpha_i - \beta_i} \cdots p_k^{2\alpha_k} \leq g$. So that the induced addition chain has length 3. Note that when g is prime, the factor method produces a g -addition chain of length at least $e + 3$ for $g^e (g + 1)^2$.

In the case $k = 1$, the factor method induces the g -addition chain

$$1, p_k^{\alpha_k - 1}, p_k^{\alpha_k}, p_k^{2\alpha_k - 1}, p_k^{2\alpha_k} \text{ if } \alpha_k > 1,$$

and

$$1, p_k - 1, p_k, p_k(p_k - 1), p_k^2 \text{ if } \alpha_k = 1.$$

Note that both are of length 4.

Example 2.2. Consider $d = g^2$, where $g = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ is the prime decomposition of g with $p_1 < \cdots < p_k$ and assume that $k > 1$. Then the factor method induces the g -addition chain

$$1, p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i-1}, p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i}, p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{2\alpha_i} \cdots p_k^{2\alpha_k}$$

where i and $0 < \beta_i \leq 2\alpha_i$ are the smallest integers such that $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i} \geq g$. Also, since $k > 1$, and thus $p_1^{\alpha_1} < g$, we have that $p_1^{\alpha_1+1}$ divides $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i}$, so $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i} \neq g$. Hence $p_1^{2\alpha_1} \cdots p_i^{\beta_i} > g$. This addition chain has length 3.

Note that in fact, $d = g^{e+2}$ requires at least $3+e$ steps. Indeed, the first iteration of the algorithm of the factor method produces

$$1, \text{fac}[q_1], q_1 \cdot \text{fac} \left[\frac{d}{q_1} \right]$$

for some q_1 where $g < q_1 \leq gp_k$. Since $q_1 > g$, we know that $\text{fac}[q_1]$ contributes at least 2 to the length of the chain. Now applying the algorithm to $\frac{d}{q_1}$ produces

$$1, \text{fac}[q_2], q_2 \cdot \text{fac} \left[\frac{d}{q_1 q_2} \right],$$

for some q_2 where $g < q_2 \leq gp_k$. Since $q_2 > g$, we know that $q_1 \cdot \text{fac}[q_2]$ contributes at least another 2 terms to the chain. We can repeat this argument at least

$$\log_{gp_k} g^{2+e} = \frac{\log_g g^{2+e}}{\log_g gp_k} > \frac{2+e}{2}$$

times, where each time, the length of the chain increases by 2 at least. Therefore, the final g -addition chain has length at least $3+e$.

When $k = 1$, the method induces the g -addition chain $1, p_k^{\alpha_k}, p_k^{2\alpha_k}$ of length 2.

2.2. The m -ary Method

The m -ary method consists of expressing d as $d = d_k m^k + \cdots + d_1 m + d_0$, where $0 \leq d_i < m$ for $0 \leq i \leq k = \lfloor \log_m d \rfloor$, and appending to 1 the sequence

$$m, d_k m, d_k m + d_{k-1}, (d_k m + d_{k-1})m, d_k m^2 + d_{k-1} m + d_{k-2}, \dots, (d_k m^{k-1} + \cdots + d_1)m, d$$

of length at most $\lfloor \log_m d \rfloor + \mu_m(d)$ when $m < g$. When $m \geq g$, the method begins with $1, d_k$ (if $1 < d_k < g$), $g, g+1, g+2, \dots, m-1$ and appends instead

$$\begin{aligned} & d_k \cdot \varsigma, \\ & d_k m + d_{k-1}, \\ & (d_k m + d_{k-1}) \cdot \varsigma, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & d_k m^2 + d_{k-1} m + d_{k-2}, \\
 & \quad \vdots \\
 & (d_k m^{k-1} + \dots + d_1) \cdot \varsigma, \\
 & \quad d
 \end{aligned}$$

where ς is a fixed g -addition chain for m . Only the digits d_i that are non-zero contribute a “non- ς ” step to the above sequence. Given an optimal ς , the length of the sequence produced when $m > g$ is thus at most

$$(m - g + 1) + \lfloor \log_m d \rfloor l_g(m) + (\mu_m(d) - 1). \tag{1}$$

Noting that $\ell_g(g^r) = r$ for $r \geq 1$, the expression (1) becomes

$$m - g + \lfloor \log_m d \rfloor \log_g(m) + \mu_m(d) \leq m - g + \lfloor \log_g d \rfloor + \mu_m(d) \tag{2}$$

in the important special case in which m is a power of g .

As finer optimizations, since adding $d_i < g$ to any number A can be done from 1 and A in a single g -addition chain step, we note that among the initial $g, g + 1, \dots, m - 1$, only numbers that occur as d_i for some i need be produced explicitly. We note also that expression (1) can be reduced by 1 if $d_k = 1$ or $d_k \geq g$.

When $g = 2$, this method is the same as the m -ary method described in [8].

Example 2.3. Consider $d = g^k(g + 1)^2 = g^k(g^2 + 2g + 1)$. The g -ary method induces the following g -addition chain, of length $k + 4$:

$$1, g, g + 2, g^2 + 2g, g^2 + 2g + 1, g(g^2 + 2g + 1), \dots, g^k(g^2 + 2g + 1).$$

Example 2.4. Consider $d = g^{2+k}(2g + 1) = 2g^{3+k} + g^{2+k}$. The g -ary method induces the following g -addition chain, of length $k + 5$:

$$1, 2, 2g, 2g + 1, 2g^2 + g, \dots, 2g^{3+k} + g^{2+k}.$$

Note that multiplying an integer d by g^k extends its g -addition chain obtained by the g -ary method by k elements.

2.3. The Tree Method

The tree method consists of drawing a tree, with root 1 and integer nodes such that the path from the root to the integer d constitutes a g -addition chain for d . Let M_n be the set of sums of m -tuples of $\{1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1} = n\}$, with $2 \leq m \leq g$, where $1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1} = n$ is the path from the root to the node n . At level $k + 1$, from left to right, we attach in increasing order, omitting elements already in the tree, under each element n of the preceding level k , the elements of M_n . When $g = 2$, this method is the same as the tree method described in [8].

Remark 2.5. In the following example, we solely use the argument that if an integer d is at the level k of the tree, then the integer gd is at worst at the level $k + 1$ of the tree.

Example 2.6. Consider $d = g^2(2g + 1)$. From the tree generated by the tree method, we see that g belongs to level 2, so $2g + 1$ belongs to level 3. Hence $g(2g + 1)$ is at worst at level 4, and $g^2(2g + 1)$ is at worst at level 5. So the length of the induced addition chain is at most 4.

As the number of steps in the g -addition chain for gn using the tree method is at most the one for n plus one, the tree method induces a g -addition chain of length at most $4 + k$ for $d = g^{2+k}(2g + 1)$.

2.4. Comparison of Methods

Table 1 summarizes the relative performances of our three methods on selected families of integers. The rows in the table are justified next.

Compared methods	Property of g	Witness Element/Family
factor $>$ g -ary	$g + 1$ not a power of a prime	$(g + 1)^2$
factor $>$ g -ary	$g > 2$ prime, $g + 1$ not a power of 2	$g^k(g + 1)^2$
factor $>$ g -ary	$g + 1 = p^\alpha, g > 2, p$ prime	$2p^{2\alpha}$
g -ary $>$ factor tree $>$ factor	g not a power of a prime	g^{2+k}
g -ary $>$ factor tree $>$ factor	$g = p^\alpha, p > 2$ prime, $\alpha > 1$	$2p^{k\alpha+1}$
g^2 -ary $>$ factor tree $>$ factor	g prime	$(p - 1)^2 p^{2k}$
tree $>$ g -ary		$g^{2+k}(2g + 1)$

Table 1: Comparisons of methods, with “ $A > B$ ” shorthand for “method A is strictly more efficient than method B ”; even when $g = 2$, no infinite family seems known for which the tree method is systematically outperformed by another method.

Rows 1 and 2 follow from comparing Examples 2.1 and 2.3 seen in previous sections; chain lengths are $3 < 4$ and $k + 3 < k + 4$ respectively. For row 3, consider $g = p^\alpha - 1$, with $p > 2$ prime, and $g > 2$. Let $d = 2p^{2\alpha} = 2g^2 + 4g + 2$. Then the g -ary method induces the g -addition chain

$$1, 2, 2g, 2g + 4, 2g^2 + 4g, 2g^2 + 4g + 2$$

of length 5 while the factor method induces the shorter g -addition chain $1, 2p^{\alpha-1}, 2p^\alpha, 2p^{2\alpha-1}, 2p^{2\alpha}$ of length 4.

For rows 4, 5 and 6, note that the tree method is never worse than the g -ary method. Hence in each row, the second line follows from the first. Row 4 follows from the fact that the g -ary method induces for g^{2+k} , where $k \geq 0$, the g -addition

chain $1, g, \dots, g^{2+k}$ of length $2+k$, shorter than the chain of length $3+k$ obtained in Example 2.2 by the factor method. For row 5, consider $g = p^\alpha$, with $p > 2$ prime, and $\alpha > 1$. Let $d = 2p^{k\alpha+1}$, with $k \geq 0$. The g -ary method induces the chain

$$1, 2p, 2pp^\alpha, \dots, 2pp^{k\alpha}$$

of length $k+1$, while the factor method induces the longer chain

$$1, 2p^{\alpha-1}, 2p^\alpha, 2p^{2\alpha}, \dots, 2p^{k\alpha}, 2p^{k\alpha+1}$$

of length $k+2$. For row 6, let $g = p$, with $p > 2$ prime and consider $d = (p-1)^2 p^{2k}$, where $k \geq 0$. The p^2 -ary method induces the g -addition chain

$$1, p-1, (p-1)^2, p(p-1)^2, p^2(p-1)^2, p^3(p-1)^2, \dots, p^{2k}(p-1)^2$$

of length $2+2k$. The factor method induces a longer g -addition chain of length at least $3+2k$. Indeed, since $p-1$ is even, the first iteration of the inductive algorithm of the factor method for d produces 2^2q , where q is a divisor of $(\frac{p-1}{2})^2$ such that $2^2q \geq p$. Now p does not divide $(\frac{p-1}{2})^2$ so $2^2q > p$, therefore the factor method requires two steps to produce 2^2q . Also, $q \neq (\frac{p-1}{2})^2$. Indeed, assume $\frac{p-1}{2}$ divides q . Since $2^2 \frac{p-1}{2} > p$, q would have to be equal to $\frac{p-1}{2}$. Hence, the p^2 -ary method produces a g -addition chain of length $2+2k$ for $d = (p-1)^2 p^{2k}$, shorter than the one of length at least $3+2k$ produced by the factor method.

To justify row 7, we combine examples 2.4 and 2.6 and deduce that for each g , there is an infinite set of integers d of the form $g^{2+k}(2g+1)$, where $k \geq 1$, such that the tree method induces a g -addition chain of length at most $4+k$ shorter than the one by the g -ary method of length $k+5$.

2.5. Practical Issues

Suppose that $g \geq 2$ is a fixed integer. As Theorem 3.1 below makes clear, the m -ary method with $m = g$ implies that the length of an optimal g -addition chain for a number d is no longer than twice $\log_g(d)$. Two computational problems thus arise:

Given d in binary or decimal notation, compute:

- (1) an optimal g -addition chain for d ;
- (2) a g -addition chain for d no longer than twice the optimal.

In complexity theory, efficiency as a first approximation is taken to mean “the existence of an algorithm that runs in time bounded by some polynomial in terms of the problem input length”. At present, no efficient algorithm is known to solve problem (1) even when $g = 2$.

But we note that problem (2) is solved efficiently by the m -ary method (Sketch: efficient arithmetic to compute the g -ary representation of d from its binary or decimal expansion is well-known [8], and a straightforward implementation of the

method involves a polynomial number of further arithmetic operations.) On the other hand, the factor method, if it solves problem (2) at all, is inefficient because it repeatedly requires factoring numbers (applied to a number d having all its prime factors larger than g , the method would actually factor d on the fly), for which no efficient algorithm is currently known. For its part, the tree method does solve problem (2), but inefficiently because it potentially examines every number less than d , hence exponentially many numbers in terms of the number of digits in the binary or decimal expansion of d .

3. Asymptotic Behavior of $l_g(d)$

For any $g \geq 2$ and $d \geq 1$, we have $l_g(d) \leq l_2(d) \leq (g - 1)l_g(d)$. Coarse asymptotic upper bounds on $l_g(d)$ thus follow from known bounds on $l_2(d)$. Such coarse bounds vastly overestimate $l_g(d)$ however. In this section, we provide finer bounds that capture its asymptotic behavior.

Theorem 3.1 and Proposition 3.2 are straightforward adaptations of the reasoning for $g = 2$.

Theorem 3.1. *For all $d \in \mathbb{N}$,*

$$\lceil \log_g d \rceil \leq l_g(d) \leq \lfloor \log_g d \rfloor + \mu_g(d).$$

Proof. Let $d \in \mathbb{N}$. And let $a_0 = 1, a_1, \dots, a_r = d$ be a g -addition chain for d of minimal length $l_g(d)$. For all i such that $1 \leq i \leq r$, we have $a_i \leq ga_{i-1}$. Therefore, $d = a_r \leq g^r$, and hence $\log_g d \leq \log_g g^r = r = l_g(d)$. Since $l_g(d)$ is an integer, $\lceil \log_g d \rceil \leq l_g(d)$.

To establish the upper bound, we use the g -ary method (with $m = g$). We get a g -addition chain of length

$$l_g(d) \leq \lfloor \log_g d \rfloor + \mu_g(d)$$

as per expression (2). □

Proposition 3.2. *For all $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, $l_g(mn) \leq l_g(m) + l_g(n)$.*

Proof. A g -addition chain for mn is given by a g -addition chain for m of length $l_g(m)$ followed by $m \cdot \varsigma$ where ς is a g -addition chain for n of length $l_g(n)$. □

The following definition respects the choice of nomenclature in the litterature for $g = 2$.

Definition 3.3. Step i is a g -step if $a_i = ga_{i-1}$.

Adapting Brauer and Erdős' developments in the case $g = 2$, we prove that the asymptotic main term of $l_g(n)$ is larger than $\lambda_g(n) + \frac{\lambda_g(n)}{8g \log_e g \lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))}$ and smaller than $\lambda_g(n) + \frac{\lambda_g(n)}{\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))}$.

Theorem 3.4. For all $g \geq 2$, we have $l_g(n) \leq \lambda_g(n) + (1 + o(1)) \frac{\lambda_g(n)}{\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))}$. (This result is in [8] in the case $g = 2$.)

Proof. Let $m = g^k$ for any $k \geq 1$. Expression (2) implies that

$$l_g(n) \leq m + \log_g n + \mu_m(n) \leq g^k + (k + 1) \log_{g^k} n.$$

So the number of steps is bounded by

$$g^k + (k + 1) \log_g n \frac{\log_g g}{\log_g g^k} = g^k + \frac{k + 1}{k} \log_g n.$$

Let

$$k = \lfloor \lambda_g(\lambda_g(n)) - 2\lambda_g(\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))) \rfloor.$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_g(n) \leq l_g(n) &\leq g^{\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n)) - 2\lambda_g(\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n)))} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lfloor \lambda_g(\lambda_g(n)) - 2\lambda_g(\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))) \rfloor}\right) \log_g n \\ &\leq \log_g n + \frac{g^2 \lambda_g(n)}{\lambda_g^2(\lambda_g(n))} + \frac{\log_g n}{\lfloor \lambda_g(\lambda_g(n)) - 2\lambda_g(\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))) \rfloor}. \end{aligned}$$

We have $\frac{\log_g n}{\lfloor \lambda_g(\lambda_g(n)) - 2\lambda_g(\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))) \rfloor} = (1 + o(1)) \frac{\lambda_g(n)}{\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))}$ since

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log_g n}{\lambda_g(n)} \frac{\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))}{\lfloor \lambda_g(\lambda_g(n)) - 2\lambda_g(\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))) \rfloor} - 1 = 0.$$

Also, $\frac{g^2 \lambda_g(n)}{\lambda_g^2(\lambda_g(n))} = o(1) \frac{\lambda_g(n)}{\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))}$ since

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{g^2}{\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))} = 0.$$

□

Corollary 3.5. For all $g \geq 2$, we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{l_g(n)}{\lambda_g(n)} = 1$. (This result is in [2] in the case $g = 2$.)

Proof. It is enough to see that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(1 + o(1))\lambda_g(n)}{\lambda_g(n)\lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))} = 0$. □

Exploiting Erdős' ideas in the case $g = 2$ as in [5], and developing the necessary tools, we show that the main term is larger than $\lambda_g(n) + \frac{\lambda_g(n)}{8g \log_e g \lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))}$.

Theorem 3.6. *Let $g \geq 3$, and let $\varepsilon > 0$. Then,*

$$\left| \left\{ g\text{-addition chains } 1 = a_0 < \dots < a_r = n \text{ with } \lambda_g(n) = m \text{ and } r \leq m + \frac{(1 - \varepsilon)m}{8g \log_e g \lambda_g(m)} \right\} \right| = \alpha^m \tag{3}$$

for $\alpha < g$ and m large enough. In other words, the number of g -addition chains short enough is substantially less than $(g - 1)g^m$, which is the number of n such that $\lambda_g(n) = m$, for m large enough.

Proof. Consider an addition chain

$$1 = a_0 < \dots < a_r = n \text{ with } \lambda_g(n) = m.$$

Fix a positive integer $K < g$. Let A_0 be the number of g -steps in this chain. For such steps, for $i \geq 2$, we have $a_i \leq g^2 a_{i-2}$, and for $i = 1$, we have $a_1 = ga_0 = g$. For $1 \leq k \leq K$, let A_k be the number of steps i such that

$$a_i = (g - k)a_{i-1} + a_{j_1} + \dots + a_{j_h},$$

$a_{i-1} > a_{j_1} \geq \dots \geq a_{j_h}$, $h \leq k$ and where $g - k$ is the largest coefficient of a_{i-1} among the coefficients of a_{i-1} in the different possible decompositions of a_i . For such steps, for $i \geq 2$,

$$a_i \leq (g - k)a_{i-1} + ka_{i-2} \leq (g(g - k) + k)a_{i-2}.$$

For $i = 1$, $a_i \leq (g - k)a_0 = g - k \leq (g(g - k) + k)$. Finally, let B be the number of steps i such that $a_i = ca_{i-1} + a_{j_1} + \dots + a_{j_h}$, $c < g - K$, $a_{i-1} > a_{j_1} \geq \dots \geq a_{j_h}$, $h + c \leq g$ and where c is the largest coefficient of a_{i-1} among the coefficients of a_{i-1} in the different possible decompositions of a_i . For such steps, for $i \geq 2$,

$$a_i < (g - K)a_{i-1} + Ka_{i-2} \leq (g(g - K) + K)a_{i-2}.$$

For $i = 1$, we have $a_i < (g - K)a_0 = g - K \leq (g(g - K) + K)$. Now, $r = A_0 + B + \sum_{k=1}^K A_k$. We have one possibility for a step accounted for in A_0 , at most r^k possibilities (regardless of where the step occurs) for a step accounted for in A_k , and at most r^g possibilities for a step accounted for in B . Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} g^{2m} &\leq a_r^2 \leq g^{2A_0+1}(g(g - K) + K)^B \prod_{k=1}^K (g(g - k) + k)^{A_k} \\ &= gg^{2r} \left(1 - \frac{K}{g} + \frac{K}{g^2}\right)^B \prod_{k=1}^K \left(1 - \frac{k}{g} + \frac{k}{g^2}\right)^{A_k}. \end{aligned}$$

Taking logarithms in base e , and using

$$\log_e\left(1 - \frac{k}{g} + \frac{k}{g^2}\right) \leq -\frac{k}{g} + \frac{k}{g^2} = \frac{k - gk}{g^2} \text{ and } \log_e\left(1 - \frac{K}{g} + \frac{K}{g^2}\right) \leq \frac{K - gK}{g^2},$$

we get

$$\frac{gK - K}{g^2}B + \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{gk - k}{g^2}A_k \leq 2\left(r - m + \frac{1}{2}\right)\log_e g. \tag{4}$$

Now

$$(3) \leq \sum_{\substack{A_0+B+\sum_{k=1}^K A_k=r \\ \frac{gK-K}{g^2}B+\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{gk-k}{g^2}A_k \leq 2\left(r-m+\frac{1}{2}\right)\log_e g}} \frac{r!}{A_0!B! \prod_{k=1}^K A_k!} r^{gB} \prod_{k=1}^K r^{kA_k}. \tag{5}$$

The number of terms in the sum (5) is bounded by $3g(K+1)(r-m+\frac{1}{2})\log_e g$ since $B, A_k, k = 1, \dots, K$ are bounded by $3g(r-m+\frac{1}{2})\log_e g$. Also,

$$\frac{r!}{A_0!} \leq r^{r-A_0} = r^{B+\sum_{k=1}^K A_k}.$$

Finally, taking into account that

$$r^{(K-\frac{K}{g})B+\sum_{k=1}^K (k-\frac{k}{g})A_k} \leq r^{2\left(r-m+\frac{1}{2}\right)g \log_e g},$$

we obtain:

$$(5) \leq 3g(K+1)\left(r - m + \frac{1}{2}\right)\log_e g \times r^{B+\sum_{k=1}^K A_k} \times r^{2\left(r-m+\frac{1}{2}\right)g \log_e g} r^{(g-K+\frac{K}{g})B+\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{k}{g}A_k}. \tag{6}$$

Choosing $K = \lceil \frac{g}{2} \rceil$ implies

$$6\left(r - m + \frac{1}{2}\right)g \log_e g \geq 3\left(K - \frac{K}{g}\right)B + \sum_{k=1}^K 3\left(k - \frac{k}{g}\right)A_k \geq \left(g - K + \frac{K}{g} + 1\right)B + \left(\frac{k}{g} + 1\right)A_k$$

in both cases when g is even or odd. Therefore,

$$(6) \leq 3(K+1)(r-m)\log_e g \times r^{8\left(r-m+\frac{1}{2}\right)g \log_e g} \tag{7}$$

Upon taking \log_g in order to compare with $\log_g((g-1)g^m) = \log_g(g-1) + m$, we get:

$$\log_g(7) = \log_g(3g(K+1)(r-m)\log_e g) + \left(8\left(r - m + \frac{1}{2}\right)g \log_e g\right)\log_g r \tag{8}$$

Using $r - m \leq (1 - \varepsilon)\frac{m}{8g \log_e g \lambda_g(m)}$, and $r \leq 2m$, and letting m go to infinity, we see that (8) is less than m . □

Corollary 3.7. *Let $g \geq 3$. For almost all n ,*

$$l_g(n) \geq \lambda_g(n) + \frac{\lambda_g(n)}{8g \log_e g \lambda_g(\lambda_g(n))},$$

i.e., the proportion of integers not satisfying this inequality goes to zero when n goes to infinity.

4. Open Questions

Many questions regarding 2-addition chains remain unsettled. Their g -analogs seem interesting and are at least as hard.

Recall the Scholz-Brauer’s conjecture [9], concerned with the worst case behavior of the 2-ary method when $g = 2$: the conjecture states that for all $n \geq 1$,

$$l_2(2^n - 1) \leq n - 1 + l_2(n).$$

Brauer [2] and Hansen [7] established a similar inequality, where certain restrictions are imposed on the 2-addition chain, yet the conjecture remains open. What can we say about

$$l_g((g^n - 1) + (g + 2g^2 + \dots + (g - 2)g^{g-2}))$$

which seems to be the worst case for the g -ary method?

The conjecture

$$l_2(n) \geq \lambda_2(n) + \lceil \log_2(\mu_2(n)) \rceil$$

also remains open, although Schönhage showed that

$$l_2(n) \geq \lceil \log_2(n) + \log_2(\mu_2(n)) - 2.13 \rceil$$

in [10]. Can we prove a similar result for arbitrary g ?

The functions $d_g(r) = |\{\text{solutions to } l_g(n) = r\}|$, $c_g(r) = \min \{n \mid l_g(n) = r\}$, as well as $NMC_g(n) = |\{g\text{-addition chains of minimal length for } n\}|$, would be interesting to study; is $d_g(r)$ increasing? How does it evolve asymptotically? These functions are not well understood, even in the case $g = 2$.

Knuth’s interest [8] in addition chains arose from the fact that $l_2(d)$ is precisely the optimum number of steps required by a *straight-line* $\{\times\}$ -program computing the univariate polynomial $q(x) = x^d$ out of the initial polynomial $q_0(x) = x$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{step 1: } & q_1 \leftarrow q_0 \times q_0 \\ & \vdots \\ \text{step } k: & q_k \leftarrow q_{k_1} \times q_{k_2}, \quad k_1, k_2 < k, \\ & \vdots \\ \text{step } l_2(d): & q \leftarrow q_i \times q_j, \quad i, j < l_2(d). \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, $l_g(d)$ for $g > 2$ captures the optimum length of such a $\{\times\}$ -program for x^d in which each step now carries out the product of up to g factors. More interestingly, $\{+, -, \times\}$ -programs, in which the initial polynomials are 1 and x and a step can now perform $q_i + q_j$ or $q_i - q_j$ or $q_i \times q_j$, are a crucial object of study in algebraic complexity theory [3]. A peripheral yet nagging question in that model has remained open since the 1970's [1, p. 26]: does there exist a polynomial $q \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$ computable by a $\{+, -, \times\}$ -program that uses *fewer* than $l_2(\text{degree}(q))$ product steps? The answer at first glance is a resounding “no”, until one realizes that cancellation of terms of degree higher than $\text{degree}(q)$ could be helpful. Such a possibility is tied to the behavior of the $l_2(d)$ function. The same question now arises in the setting generalized to g -ary $\{+, -, \times\}$ -programs and $l_g(d)$ for $g > 2$.

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